

Extraction Studies of Niobium(V) with *n-m*-Tolyl-*p*-Methoxybenzohydroxamic Acid (TMBHA)

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The present communication deals with the various aspects of Nb(V)—TMBHA extraction studies in water-chloroform-system. In 1-8 *M* hydrochloric acid medium, this reagent forms a greenish-yellow coloured complex with niobium(V) which can be extracted into chloroform. The composition of the complex is found to be 1:2 with respect to niobium and reagent (TMBHA). The stepwise conditional stability constants of this complex also have been determined by Yatsimirskii's and Leden's methods.

RECENTLY *N-m*-tolyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) has been used for the solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V)¹. This reagent has been found to form coloured chelates with various metal ions². The extraction studies of niobium(V) with this reagent (TMBHA) has not been carried out so far and hence it is undertaken for the first time in this laboratory.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents

Standard niobium solution was prepared in tartaric acid³. The niobium content was estimated gravimetrically with 8-hydroxyquinoline⁴.

The reagent (TMBHA) was synthesised by the method as described by earlier workers.⁵ Fresh solutions of the reagent in distilled chloroform were used.

A Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

General Procedure :

An aliquot of niobium solution containing 2-20 μg of Nb(V) was taken and to it added enough concentrated hydrochloric acid so as to make acid strength in the range 1-8*M*. The total volume of aqueous phase was made to 10 ml with distilled water. Aqueous phase was equilibrated with 10 ml of reagent solution in chloroform for 10 min. The absorbance of the extracted complex was measured at 320 nm against the similarly processed reagent as a blank. The amount of Nb extracted was computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Spectral Properties

It is shown in Figure 1 that reagent (TMBHA)

has an absorption maximum at 255 nm ($\epsilon = 1.5 \times 10^4$) and the greenish-yellow coloured complex at 320 nm ($\epsilon = 2.15 \times 10^4$). The system obeys Beer's law within the concentration range of 0.02 to 4.0 μg Nb(V) ml^{-1} of chloroform. The effective working range was found to be 0.8-2.5 μg Nb(V) ml^{-1} of chloroform by Ringbom curve. The Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 320 nm is 0.0043 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$.² The complex is stable for 24 hrs.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Nb(V)-TMBHA complex.

- --- ○ Complex against reagent blank—
Nb(V) = 4.0×10^{-5} *M*
- --- ● reagent blank against Chloroform
TMBHA = 3.7×10^{-5} *M*

Effect of concentration of acid and MgCl_2

The extent of Nb (15 μg) extraction increases with the increase in concentration of hydrochloric acid within the range of 1.0 to 8.0*M*. The effect of increasing MgCl_2 concentration (3.0 to 8.0*M*) at fixed hydrochloric acid concentration (2.5*M*) also shows the increase in the extent of Nb extraction. The extraction was also studied at fixed ionic strength (4.0*M* MgCl_2) and different hydrogen ion concentration. The results reveal that extraction is also a function of hydrogen ion concentration. The

values of per cent extraction (%E) and distribution ratio (D) at various acidity are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

EXTRACTION OF Nb(V)-TMBHA COMPLEX AS A FUNCTION OF HYDROCHLORIC ACID CONCENTRATION, Nb(V)=15 μ g; [TMBHA]= $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ IN CHLOROFORM

Molarity of HCl	Per cent. extraction %E	Distribution ratio D
1.0	13.58	0.1572
2.0	17.60	0.2137
3.0	23.20	0.3022
4.0	37.60	0.6028
4.5	52.01	1.0838
5.0	75.18	3.0307
5.5	90.40	9.4249
6.0	95.19	19.79
7.0	96.03	24.03
8.0	98.40	61.3729
9.0	98.40	61.3729

Effect of reagent concentration

Niobium (15 μ g) was extracted with different concentrations of reagent varying from 4.0×10^{-5} to $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. The per cent. extraction varies between 7.0 to 98.0% within the concentration range of 4.0×10^{-5} to $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent and remains constant thereafter. Therefore $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent was used for extraction.

Effect of solvents

Amongst the several solvents tried (benzene, carbon tetrachloride, isoamyl alcohol, isobutanol and chloroform), chloroform was preferred because of high sensitivity of reagent in it and its high extractability towards Nb-complex. The absorbance values for the solvents given above are 0.500, 0.490, 0.310, 0.480 and 0.550 respectively.

Time of equilibrium

The aqueous phase was equilibrated from 1 to 30 min. The per cent. extraction for times 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 min is 64, 75, 90, 95 and 98 respectively. However, after 5 min, per cent. extraction remains constant and hence a time of 10 min was arbitrarily chosen for entire extraction studies.

Effect of diverse ions

Most of the associated cations do not interfere with the determination of Nb(V) in large excess— Fe^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , VO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} can be tolerated in more than 100 times excess. About 25 times excess Ta^{5+} can be tolerated. The most interfering cations are Ti^{4+} , $Mo_2O_7^{4-}$, WO_4^{2-} , V^{5+} , and Sn^{2+} . Of the various anions and complexing agents, F^- interferes seriously. Br^- , I^- , SO_4^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , $S_2O_8^{2-}$, BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} , can be tolerated in large excess. Citrate, acetate, and EDTA do not interfere. About 800 times excess oxalate can be tolerated.

From ten determinations with 15 μ g of niobium the absorbance was found to be 0.460 ± 0.010 at

320 nm. Average and maximum relative deviation were found to be 0.52% and 0.74% respectively. The total operation requires about 30 min.

Composition of the extractable species

The fact that the extraction is dependent on acid, reagent and $MgCl_2$ concentration, indicates the important role of all these factors in the formation of extractable species.

By varying the hydrochloric acid concentration from 1.0 to 8.0M its distribution ratio $D_{(Nb)}$, dependence indicates liberation of two protons in the extraction system.

A plot of $\log D_{(Nb)}$ versus $\log [H^+]$ at fixed chloride ion concentration (8.0M) gives a slope of two. Similarly a plot of $\log D_{(Nb)}$ versus $\log [Cl^-]$ at fixed $[H^+]$ (2.5M) shows a slope of two. These observations clearly show the liberation of two protons and two chloride ions in the reaction.

The extraction reaction therefore, can be written as :

where, HR = TMBHA.

Thus, the probable extractable species might be $NbOClR_2$. The stoichiometric ratio of Nb:HR for the formation of extractable neutral complex of fixed hydrochloric acid concentration (2.5M) and 5.0M chloride ion concentration has been observed to be 1:2. This composition is supported by Job's⁶ method as applied by Kabad⁷ for liquid-liquid extraction studies and mole ratio⁸ method. This composition has further been confirmed by a plot of $\log D_{(Nb)}$ versus $\log [TMBHA]_{org}$ (concentration of TMBHA in organic phase at equilibrium) which gave a slope of two.

Metal-ligand stability constants

The conditional metal ligand stepwise stability constants of the extracted complex were computed from the spectrophotometric data by Yatsimirskii's^{9,10} and Leden's¹¹ methods. The values of stability constants by these methods are found to be $\log K_1 = 3.99$, $\log K_2 = 3.51$ by Yatsimirskii's method and $\log K_1 = 4.02$, $\log K_2 = 3.32$ by Leden's method.

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